

DIGITAL SERVICE QUALITY, ETHICAL PRACTICES AND WORK LOCATION: INFLUENCE ON EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION IN AN ESL COMPANY

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location influence employee satisfaction in the English as a Second Language (ESL) industry, where limited studies have simultaneously explored these variables within hybrid work environments. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, data were collected from 159 employees through a structured survey questionnaire. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation, were used to assess employee perceptions, while inferential tools such as independent samples t-test, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis determined relationships and predictive influence. Results showed that employees reported generally high levels of digital service quality and ethical practices, particularly in fairness, transparency, and respectful treatment. Work location analysis revealed that office-based employees demonstrated higher satisfaction compared to home-based employees. Regression analysis indicated that the overall model significantly predicted employee satisfaction. Company ethical practices emerged as the strongest significant predictor, while work location also showed a significant influence. However, digital service quality did not show a significant influence on employee satisfaction, suggesting that technological systems may function as a basic requirement rather than a motivating factor. This study addresses the gap in ESL-focused research by providing empirical evidence on how ethical climate, digital systems, and work arrangements jointly affect employee satisfaction. Findings highlight the importance of strengthening ethical leadership and organizational support alongside maintaining reliable digital infrastructure.

Future studies may include additional variables such as work engagement, leadership style, and work–life balance.

Keywords: *Digital Service Quality, Ethical Practices, Employee Satisfaction, Work Location, ESL Industry*

INTRODUCTION

The global expansion of the English as a Second Language (ESL) industry has been driven by the increasing demand for English proficiency in education, the workplace, and international communication (Crystal, 2012; Graddol, 2019). ESL programs enable learners in countries such as China, Japan, and Korea to enhance their English skills and gain access to broader academic and professional opportunities in a globalized environment (Butler, 2015; Huang, 2018). To meet this growing demand, the Philippines has emerged as one of the leading providers of ESL services due to its highly proficient English-speaking workforce, competitive labor costs, and qualified teachers (Cabigon, 2015). Philippine ESL companies deliver language education through online platforms that allow real-time interaction between teachers and students. Consequently, these organizations rely heavily on digital technologies such as learning management systems, scheduling tools, and video conferencing platforms to ensure effective service delivery (Hrastinski, 2008; Martin & Bolliger, 2018).

In recent years, several ESL companies have established operations in Cagayan de Oro City, contributing to local employment and the growth of the digital service economy. These companies employ both office-based and home-based instructors who conduct classes using online learning platforms, video conferencing tools, and time-tracking systems. Although ESL companies primarily provide language education, their business model closely resembles that of Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) organizations, as they deliver outsourced services to international clients and depend heavily on information and communication technologies (De Guzman & Lapid, 2020). Similar to BPO firms, ESL organizations employ a large number of service providers who interact with foreign clients through digital platforms, with performance often measured based on efficiency, service quality, and customer satisfaction (Lorenzo & Padilla, 2021).

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has significantly transformed the working environment of ESL organizations. Employees rely on digital tools such as learning management systems (LMS), online booking systems, and video conferencing applications to deliver lessons, manage schedules, and communicate with students. As these technologies serve as the primary medium for service delivery, the quality, reliability, and responsiveness of digital systems are critical factors influencing employees' work experiences. Efficient systems and accessible technical support enhance productivity and job satisfaction, whereas unstable platforms, delayed support, and system interruptions may lead to frustration and decreased employee morale (Li, 2022; Alavi & Ahuja, 2023).

In addition to technological infrastructure, ethical organizational practices play a vital role in shaping employees' workplace experiences. Ethical practices include fair treatment, transparent policies, responsible monitoring, and the protection of employees' personal information. In digitally mediated workplaces such as ESL companies, monitoring systems are often used to track teaching performance, attendance, and productivity. When these systems are implemented fairly and transparently, they promote trust and organizational commitment. However, when employees perceive monitoring practices as unfair or lacking transparency, it may result in dissatisfaction and disengagement (Martin et al., 2022; Hu, 2024).

Employees in the Philippine ESL industry, particularly in Cagayan de Oro City, operate under different work arrangements, including office-based and home-based setups. Office-based employees typically work within company premises, where they receive direct supervision and immediate technical support. In contrast, home-based instructors conduct lessons remotely and rely on stable internet connectivity, personal devices, and remote technical assistance. These differences in work environments may influence employees' experiences with digital systems and their perceptions of organizational practices and ethics. As such, work location becomes an important factor in understanding variations in employee satisfaction within ESL organizations (Joo & Lee, 2021; Ghosh et al., 2021).

Despite the growing contribution of the ESL industry to the Philippine digital economy, existing literature on digital service quality and workplace ethics primarily focuses on customer satisfaction or traditional BPO contexts, with limited attention to employees' perspectives in ESL organizations. Previous studies have established that digital system quality and ethical practices significantly influence employee satisfaction and work performance. However, there remains a lack of empirical research examining these variables simultaneously within ESL settings, particularly when considering differences in work location (Ramirez & Cruz, 2019; Carcido & Chavez, 2024). Addressing this gap is essential in supporting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), which emphasizes productive employment and employee well-being, as well as SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), which promotes sustainable and inclusive technological development (United Nations, 2015). Therefore, further research is needed to examine how digital service quality and ethical practices influence employee satisfaction in ESL organizations.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study examines the influence of digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location on employee satisfaction in digitally mediated ESL organizations. The framework is anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), the E-SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Malhotra, 2005), Organizational Justice Theory (Colquitt, 2001), and Social Exchange Theory. These theories collectively explain how digital systems and ethical organizational practices shape employees' attitudes, perceptions, and overall satisfaction across different work environments.

Digital Service Quality is the first independent variable and refers to the reliability, efficiency, and responsiveness of digital platforms used in organizational operations. Based on the Technology Acceptance Model, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use influence individuals' acceptance of technology (Davis, 1989). When employees perceive digital systems as efficient and easy to use, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward these systems, leading to increased satisfaction. In ESL organizations, where instruction and communication are delivered primarily through digital platforms, system reliability and usability are critical determinants of employee satisfaction (Li, 2022; Lorenzo & Padilla, 2021; Alavi & Ahuja, 2023; Joo & Lee, 2021).

To further operationalize digital service quality, this study adopts the E-SERVQUAL framework, which evaluates electronic service quality across four dimensions: system availability, fulfillment, privacy, and responsiveness (Parasuraman et al., 2005).

System availability refers to the reliability, stability, and accessibility of digital platforms. Consistent system performance minimizes disruptions and enhances employees' confidence in organizational technologies. Empirical studies indicate that reliable digital infrastructure significantly improves job satisfaction and reduces work-related stress in technology-driven environments (Li, 2022; Kaur & Sharma, 2021; Alavi & Ahuja, 2023).

Fulfillment pertains to the extent to which digital systems perform their intended functions and meet user expectations. In ESL organizations, this includes effective lesson delivery, accurate scheduling, and efficient communication. Consistent service performance strengthens trust in organizational systems and positively influences user satisfaction (Büyüközkan, 2020; Alshurideh et al., 2022; Kaur & Sharma, 2021).

Privacy involves the protection of personal and organizational data processed through digital platforms. Strong data protection practices enhance trust and reduce concerns regarding information misuse. Prior studies emphasize that transparent data management and secure systems contribute significantly to employee trust and satisfaction in digital work environments (Lee, 2023; Martin et al., 2022; Hu, 2024).

Responsiveness refers to the promptness and effectiveness of technical support when issues arise. Timely assistance reduces frustration and reinforces employees' perceptions of organizational support, thereby enhancing satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 2005; Joo & Lee, 2021; Hu, 2024).

The second independent variable is Company Ethical Practices, grounded in Organizational Justice Theory. Ethical practices are conceptualized through three dimensions: distributive, procedural, and interactional justice (Colquitt, 2001).

Distributive justice refers to the perceived fairness of outcomes such as compensation, workload, and recognition. When employees perceive equitable distribution of rewards and responsibilities, their level of satisfaction increases.

Procedural justice relates to the fairness, consistency, and transparency of organizational decision-making processes. Fair procedures enhance trust in management and foster positive employee attitudes.

Interactional justice focuses on the quality of interpersonal treatment employees receive from supervisors, including respect, honesty, and professionalism. Positive interpersonal interactions contribute significantly to employees' sense of value and organizational commitment.

Empirical evidence confirms that these dimensions of justice are strong predictors of job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Colquitt et al., 2013). Ethical leadership and transparent governance further strengthen trust and workplace harmony (Trevino & Nelson, 2017). In digital work environments, ethical practices related to monitoring, data privacy, and accountability are particularly critical in maintaining employee well-being (Floridi et al., 2018; Lee, 2023; Hu, 2024). Studies in the Philippine ESL context also highlight that ethical management practices significantly enhance employee morale and satisfaction (De Guzman & Lapid, 2020; Ramirez & Cruz, 2019; Carcido & Chavez, 2024).

Work Location is the third independent variable and refers to the physical or virtual setting in which employees perform their duties. In the ESL industry, employees typically operate under either office-based or home-based arrangements. These work environments influence access to organizational resources, supervision, technical support, and collaboration.

Home-based work offers flexibility, autonomy, and reduced commuting time but may also present challenges such as unstable internet connectivity, limited technical support, and reduced interaction with supervisors. In contrast, office-based work provides structured environments, immediate supervision, and direct access to organizational resources and support systems. These differences significantly influence employees' experiences with digital systems and their perceptions of organizational support (Joo & Lee, 2021; Ghosh et al., 2021).

Employee Satisfaction is the dependent variable in this study and is defined as a positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation of one's job and work environment (Locke, 1976). Contemporary research extends this concept to include perceptions of digital support, technological reliability, and ethical leadership in modern organizations (Li, 2022; Lee, 2023; Hu, 2024).

Employee satisfaction encompasses both cognitive and emotional components. Cognitive appraisal involves employees' evaluation of job conditions, including digital system effectiveness, fairness of policies, workload distribution, and availability of support resources. Emotional responses, on the other hand, reflect feelings such as satisfaction, motivation, or frustration, which arise from daily workplace experiences. Positive cognitive evaluations and emotional experiences contribute to higher levels of job satisfaction, while negative experiences may lead to disengagement.

In this study, employee satisfaction is viewed as a function of digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location. Employees are more likely to experience higher satisfaction, reduced stress, and stronger organizational commitment when digital systems are reliable and organizational practices are perceived as fair and transparent.

Research Question

1. What are the employees' assessments of the digital service quality of the ESL Company in terms of:
 - 1.1 System Availability;
 - 1.2 Fulfillment;
 - 1.3 Privacy; and
 - 1.4 Responsiveness?
2. What are the participants' assessments of the ethical practices of the ESL Company in terms of:
 - 2.1 Distributive Justice;
 - 2.2 Procedural Justice; and
 - 2.3 Interactional Justice?
3. What is the distribution of participants according to their work location (home-based or office-based)?
4. Do the participants' level of satisfaction significantly differ considering work location?
5. Do digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location significantly influence employee satisfaction?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the influence of digital service quality and ethical practices on employee satisfaction. Descriptive-correlational research describes relationships between variables without manipulating them. Quantitative research aims to measure attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors while generalizing findings from a defined population by generating numerical data (Creswell, John W. & Creswell, J. David, 2018; Mohajan, Haradhan Kumar, 2020).

By combining descriptive and correlational elements, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of how digital service quality and ethical practices relate to employee satisfaction. The design allowed the researcher to analyze naturally occurring relationships among the variables without experimental intervention.

Participants and Sampling Procedure

Data were collected using a structured, paper-based questionnaire administered to eligible ESL employees within the selected organization during official working hours,

ensuring that responses reflected actual perceptions of digital service quality, ethical practices, and employee satisfaction. A total of 160 employees participated in the study, a sample size consistent with recommended guidelines for correlational research and Structural Equation Modeling, which suggest 150–300 respondents to ensure statistical reliability and adequate power.

Total enumeration sampling was employed, wherein all accessible and qualified employees from the identified departments were included as respondents. This approach ensured comprehensive representation of the target population, minimized sampling bias, and enhanced the accuracy of the findings. Participants were selected based on their availability and eligibility at the time of data collection.

The questionnaires were administered on-site to ensure reliable and complete responses. During data processing, one response was excluded due to being identified as an outlier, resulting in a final dataset suitable for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Data gathered from the structured questionnaire were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. Mean scores and standard deviations were computed to determine employees' assessments of digital service quality, ethical practices, and employee satisfaction. Responses were interpreted using a predefined Likert scale to describe the level of agreement for each indicator.

For Research Question 1–3, descriptive statistics including frequency distribution, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were utilized to describe employees' perceptions of digital service quality dimensions, ethical practices, and employee satisfaction levels.

For Research Question 4, Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was employed to determine the relationship between digital service quality and employee satisfaction, as well as between ethical practices and employee satisfaction. This statistical technique measured the strength and direction of associations among variables.

For Research Question 5, multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the extent to which digital service quality and ethical practices significantly influence employee satisfaction. The analysis identified the predictive contribution of each independent variable while controlling for shared variance. Statistical assumptions such as normality, linearity, independence, and homoscedasticity were examined to ensure validity of the results.

All statistical analyses were performed at a 0.05 level of significance, ensuring reliability and accuracy in interpreting the findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. How do employees assess the digital service quality of the ESL Company in terms of:

- 1.1 System Availability;**
- 1.2 Fulfillment;**
- 1.3 Privacy; and**
- 1.4 Responsiveness?**

Table 1 the summary of the rating of the digital service quality provided by the ESL Company by employees on four dimensions: system availability, fulfillment, privacy, and responsiveness are given in table 5. The findings indicate that the system availability ($M = 4.38$), fulfillment ($M = 4.45$), privacy ($M = 4.36$), and responsiveness ($M = 4.42$) are considered to be high with the mean of 4.40 ($SD = 0.36$). The overall standard deviation is extremely low, which implies that the responses of the employees were very similar in all the dimensions, which means that they had a common positive attitude towards the organizational digital systems and services.

Table 1
Summary Table of Digital Service Quality

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
System Availability	4.38	High	0.56
Fulfillment	4.45	High	0.43
Privacy	4.36	High	0.53
Responsiveness	4.42	High	0.47
Digital Service Quality	4.40	High	0.36

Research Question 2. What is the employees' assessment of the ethical practices of the ESL Company in terms of:

- 2.1 Distributive Justice;**
- 2.2 Procedural Justice; and**
- 2.3 Interactional Justice?**

Table 2 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the perception of employees on the ethical practice of the ESL Company in its three dimensions of distributive justice, procedural justice and the interactional justice. The findings indicate that the means was 4.33 ($SD = 0.58$), which can be considered as high, so employees generally believe that the ethical standards of the organization are fair, transparent and practiced most of the time. The standard deviation was relatively low, which implies that the answers of employees were relatively stable and indicate the common positive attitude towards ethical behavior in the company. This observation is evidenced by the mean scores of the dimensions that have detected that interactional justice (4.39), procedural justice (4.31), and distributive justice (4.29) were rated as high meaning that

most of the employees concur that fairness is reflected in the way people are treated, decision making processes and distribution of outcomes.

Table 2
Summary Table of Ethical Practices

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Distributive Justice	4.29	High	0.47
Procedural Justice	4.31	High	0.55
Interactional Justice	4.39	High	0.54
Ethical Practices	4.40	High	0.39

Research Question 3. What is the participants' work location?

Table 3 displayed the frequency and percentage distribution of the participants with regard to work location. The findings revealed that 101 participants (63.52) were the office-based employees and 58 employees (36.48) were the home-based employees, which means that most of the participants had an office-based working arrangement. The distribution revealed that over fifty percent of the workforce was undertaking their roles in the conventional office environment.

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage of Participants' Work Location

Work Location	Frequency	Percentage
Office Based	101	63.52
Home Based	58	36.48

Research Question 4. Do the participants' level of satisfaction significantly differ considering work location?

Table 4 shows the findings of the independent samples t-test on the difference of employee satisfaction between the home based work location and the office based work location. The results indicate that the office-based employees (M= 4.560, SD= 0.370) were recorded to be much more satisfied than home-based employees (M= 4.218, SD= 0.278), $t(145.95) = 6.588, p < 0.01$. The null hypothesis is not accepted and therefore it means that the difference in employee satisfaction between work locations is statistically significant because the p-value calculated is less than the level of significance of 0.01. Moreover, the calculated effect size was huge (Cohen's $d = 0.99$), which implies that the

difference between the two groups is significant and statistically significant, as well as meaningful.

Table 4
Comparison of Satisfaction Levels by Work Location Using an Independent Samples t-Test

Group	n	M	Interpretation	SD	t(53)	p	Cohen's d
Home-based	58	4.218	Moderate	0.278	-6.588	.0000*	0.99
Office-based	101	4.560	High	0.370	(145.95)	*	

**Significant at 0.01 two-tailed alpha level.

Research Question 5. Do digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location significantly influence employee satisfaction?

Ho1: Digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location do not significantly influence employee satisfaction.

Ho2: Digital service quality does not significantly influence employee satisfaction.

Ho3: Company ethical practices do not significantly influence employee satisfaction

Ho4: Work Location does not significantly influence employee satisfaction.

Table 5 the regression analysis of the effect of digital service quality, ethical practices of the company and the location of work on the employee satisfaction at the ESL Company. The findings showed that the general regression equation was significant, $F = 42.857$, $p < .001$, meaning that the combination of the predictor variables significantly predicted relationship in the levels of employee satisfaction. The null hypothesis (Ho_1) can be rejected as the calculated p-value was lower than the level of significance of 0.001. The model generated a significant correlation coefficient ($R = 0.673$) indicating that there is a great positive correlation between the combined predictors and employee satisfaction.

Table 5
Regression Analysis on the Influence of Digital Service Quality, Ethical Practices, and Work Location on Employee Satisfaction

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	1.770	.337		5.257	.000
Digital Service quality	.092	.086	.088	1.066	.288
Ethical Practices	.504	.073	.525	6.927**	.000
Work location	.123	.057	.158	2.166*	.032

Model Summary

R = 0.673 $R^2 = 0.453$ Adj. $R^2 = 0.443$ $F = 42.857^{**}$ $p = .000$

**significant at 0.01 level

Conclusions

The findings revealed that digital service quality, company ethical practices, and work location collectively influenced employee satisfaction in the ESL organization. However, only ethical practices and work location showed significant individual effects, while digital service quality did not emerge as a significant predictor. This suggests that while digital systems are perceived as reliable, they function as baseline requirements, whereas fairness, transparency, and respectful treatment play a more critical role in shaping employee satisfaction. Differences in work arrangements further indicate that workplace conditions influence employees' overall evaluations.

These results support Organizational Justice Theory and Social Exchange Theory, highlighting the importance of fairness and positive organizational treatment in enhancing satisfaction. In contrast, the Technology Acceptance Model and E-SERVQUAL were only partially supported, as digital service quality did not significantly predict satisfaction.

The study contributes to the Philippine ESL context by emphasizing the importance of ethical governance and supportive work environments. However, findings are limited to a single organization, and future research may consider broader samples and longitudinal designs to improve generalizability.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed based on the findings of the study, which revealed high levels of digital service quality, ethical practices, work location and employee satisfaction within the organization, as well as differences in employee experiences across work arrangements. These recommendations aim to further strengthen existing organizational practices and sustain positive employee perceptions.

1. ESL Teachers and Employees may

1.1 keep actively working on the appropriate use of digital platforms and taking a maximum of system functions advantages to improve the work efficiency and productivity. Through enhancing digital flexibility, employees would be able to assist in streamlining operations and better service delivery.

1.2 will keep the open communication growing and will be involved in the systems of organizational feedback on ethical issues, equity, and enhancing the digital systems. Their participation can also enhance transparency, trust and collaborative working culture.

2. Company Management and Administrators may

2.1 also promote the quality of digital services through continuous monitoring of the fulfilment of the system, responsiveness, and technical reliability. The IT support may be improved by evaluating the system on a regular basis, enhancing it, and maintaining operational efficiency.

2.2 keep strengthening ethical actions through making unbiased decisions, open communication, and equal sharing of duties and rewards. Enhancing ethics training, grievance process and fairness evaluation can also maintain employee satisfaction in the long-term.

3. Human Resource Department may

3.1 further build programs that facilitate organizational justice, employee appreciation as well as promote professional growth opportunities to maintain the high rates of satisfaction among both office-based and home-based employees.

3.2 reinforce the feedback frameworks and employee engagement programs to maintain the continuous observation of the employees regarding the quality of the digital services and ethical behavior within the organization.

4. Future Researchers may

4.1 investigate other variables that could have an impact on employee satisfaction, including organizational commitment, leadership style, work engagement, readiness to digital transformation, or work-life balance.

4.2 make comparative studies in various ESL firms or services-based firms to establish whether such similar trends also exist in other organizational settings.

4.3 leverage mixed methods to supplement quantitative results with qualitative data to gain a more comprehensive knowledge about the lived experiences of the employees concerning digital systems and ethics in the workplace.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study complied with established ethical standards in research involving human participants. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee prior to data collection. Informed consent was secured from all respondents, who were informed of the study's purpose, voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained, with no personally identifiable information collected, and all data were securely stored in accordance with data privacy principles. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded, ensuring no harm was caused during the research process. The researcher declares that no conflict of interest existed, and all findings were interpreted objectively without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation of sources, and the results were used solely for academic purposes. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools was limited to grammar and language refinement only, and this is disclosed to ensure full transparency and uphold academic integrity.

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